

The Role of the Government of RW 023, Teluk Pucung Village, North Bekasi Subdistrict, Bekasi City, in Overcoming Crimes Occurring in the Community Environment

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Abstract:

Crime can occur anywhere and at any time, including in the residential environment. This is no exception for the Bekasi city community. According to the Bekasi City Central Statistics Agency, there is an increase in crime of 12% in 2021 and an increase of 75% in 2022. On this basis, an effective government role is needed to protect the community from crime in their environment, so this research was carried out with the aim of finding out the role of government in overcoming crimes that occur in society. This research was conducted in RW 023 Teluk Pucung Village, North Bekasi District, Bekasi City, West Java using qualitative descriptive methods. The data collection technique used was purposive sampling with a total of 10 people and consisted of elements of the community, RW, and local security forces. The data that has been

obtained will be analyzed using nVivo and content analysis. The conclusion from this research is that crimes across the RW 023 area vary greatly, from theft to sexual disclosures. Based on what residents and the local government (RT and RW) said, if a crime is discovered, it will be handled in the RT area. If the RT area still needs to be finished, then the handling will continue to the RW area. In handling this, people generally use family mediation techniques, although this only closes the way for litigation settlement if there is common ground in mediation.

Keywords: *Society, Crime, Government Role.*

Introduction

Indonesia is a developing country that is also a country of law. This makes Indonesia have a policy to provide sanctions and consequences for things done by Indonesian people or other things related to Indonesia in a book of laws. The Criminal Code (KUHP) is a collection of written laws that regulate what is related to criminal acts in Indonesia.

Crimes that can occur anywhere and anytime require the government, through the regulation of laws and their authority, to be able to prevent and overcome crime. One of the government's efforts in preventing and overcoming crime in the community's living environment is what the Maro Sebo Police do. Hartono (2016) in his research stated that increasing the role of the Indonesian National Police in tackling crime in Indonesia is needed in order to raise awareness and obedience in complying with existing laws,

so that order and discipline in society are realized. However, with a limited number of police officers, police institutions need synergy and collaboration with elements of society.

The efforts made by the Maro Sebo Police can actually be carried out by other Polsek that still experience high crime rates. Bekasi City is a city that is a companion to the city of Jakarta, which is one of the centres of activity on the island of Java. Based on data quoted from the Bekasi City Statistics Agency, it shows an increase in crime of 12% in 2021 and an increase of 75% in 2022. This raises the question of many parties: What made the increase in criminal acts committed in this city increase significantly? The COVID-19 pandemic, massive layoffs that have recently occurred frequently, and many other things are considered to be the cause of the significant increase in criminal crimes.

In the midst of the emergence of many hypotheses regarding this data, the researcher got a new fact about an area in Bekasi City, which is said to have an increasing and complex crime rate. From the initial data found, the problems that arise occur due to many factors. This finally made the researcher feel the need to find valid data about the role of the local government in tackling crimes that often occur in RW 023, Teluk Pucung Village, North Bekasi District, Bekasi City.

Literature Review

Society, Crime and the Role of Government

Society is a group of relatively independent people who live together for a relatively long time, occupy a specific area, have a relatively long culture, and carry out activities for quite a long time within that group. Society can also be defined as a group of people who live in a specific area, who have a division of labour that functions specifically and are interdependent and have a socio-cultural system that regulates the activities of members, who have an awareness of unity and a feeling of belonging and are able to act in an orderly manner. (M. Zaini Hasan et al, (1996: 12-13).

According to Koentjaraningrat in Usman Pelly et al. (1994: 29), society is a unity of human life that interacts according to a specific system of customs that is continuous and bound by a sense of shared identity. Furthermore, Koentjaraningrat (2002: 144) defines society as a group of people who "hang out" with each other or, in scientific terms, "interact" with each other. Due to this interaction, a sizeable social order is created between communities that form a nation or state, in which, of course, there are conflicts between the interests of fellow social beings.

Indonesia is a country with frequent conflict and crime phenomena. This is influenced by the demands of life and the environment of the criminal. The Central Statistics Agency stated that there were 294,281 crimes in Indonesia in 2018. Then, in 2020, there were 247,218 incidents with a crime clock of 00.01'47" (1 minute 47 seconds). Etymologically, crime can be defined as a crime or immoral act, where the act is considered a crime based on the nature of the act if the act harms society or individuals or materially, such as stealing, killing, robbing, raping, etc. Paul Moedikdo Moeliono (Muliadi, 2015) defines crime as an act of violating legal norms that are interpreted, or It should be interpreted by society as a detrimental, annoying act that should not be tolerated.

Crime is behaviour that challenges applicable morals and norms and can cause harm to the general public. Components that can be used to measure crime phenomena include total crime (number of crimes), crime rate (crime rate per 100,000 population), and crime clock (time lag for crime incidents). Various factors can cause a high crime rate in an area. According to (Sugiharto Lestari, 2015), these factors include economic factors, juvenile delinquency and environmental factors.

Unfavorable economic conditions accompanied by population density will influence the birth of slum areas. The presence of densely populated slum areas is equivalent to high levels of crime and low quality of life. Becker (Rocque et al., 2019) states that people who do not have a job and a steady income or are unemployed can commit criminal acts and turn into criminals.

This is influenced by the low costs required, as well as high yields or profits so that they are able to meet their daily needs.

Juvenile delinquency that has exceeded the limits can also influence the rise of robbery crimes. Teenagers who commit the crime of stealing motorbikes on the road are not just one or two people but can reach four people or even more. In general, juvenile delinquency is also caused by a broken home. In principle, the family structure is no longer complete due to things such as parental divorce or one of the parents being absent for quite an extended period one or both parents died.

The environment in question is the family and community environment, communication with friends and neighbours. These two things are factors that enable someone to commit a series of crimes. These things can be interconnected because whether a person's behaviour is good or bad is influenced by their environment. If the environment is good, their behaviour will also be good, but if the environment is bad, then perhaps their behaviour can also be bad. Crimes that commonly occur in society are conventional types of crime or can be called blue-collar crime. (Medan Area University, 2021). Conventional crime is a type of crime that defies all the rules in the Criminal Code. The phenomenon of conventional crime often occurs in society in the form of motor vehicle theft. The impacts caused by conventional crimes are in the form of physical and psychological losses. Conventional crimes that commonly occur in society include theft, cheating, rape, murder, drug abuse, and so on.

The large number of crimes that occur in society requires an influential government role. However, in its implementation, the government cannot work alone but requires other parties, especially in implementing regional government. It is on this basis that the government forms its representatives in the regions which we are more familiar with as regional governments.

The government here is defined as the Regional Government, which consists of the Regional Head and other regional apparatus. As is known, in order to implement the principle of

decentralization, the government divides regions into three parts, namely provincial regions, district regions and city regions, which have the authority to regulate and manage the interests of local communities according to their initiatives based on community aspirations. The City Government is assisted by other smaller government agencies so that they can have direct contact with the broader community, starting from the sub-districts, sub-districts, Rukun Warga (RW), to the minor government apparatus, namely the Neighborhood Association (RT).

The role of the Regional Government in providing legal protection to the community is to create security and public order in its territory. This role is an embodiment of the goal of securing the founding of the Republic of Indonesia. This is firmly stated in the main tasks of the government, which are to carry out security and order aspects as per the National.

The Role of Government in Society

The role of government in society can be defined as all efforts made by the government to protect and secure society from all forms of threats that could harm it. The scope of threats that can arise is extensive, both physical and non-physical. Threats that endanger society can be of various kinds, such as crime, colonialism, disease, natural disasters, and others, the scope of the object of which can also be the protection of life, relationships, assets, self-esteem, freedom, body and soul, and other valuable things, for society. Protection of the community as the role of the government is carried out throughout Indonesia. Government institutions from central to regional, or officials serving in remote areas, represent the presence of the state to carry out protective functions. One of the implications of the existence of a community protection function is the government's obligation to provide security and safety for the community. This is increasingly important, along with the emergence of various types of threats that endanger society, such as crime in the community's living environment. (Sutiyo & Eva, 2023).

Method

This research uses descriptive qualitative research. Bogdan and Tylor define qualitative research as a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people or observed behaviour (Achmad & Ida, 2018). The descriptive qualitative method adjusts the opinions of researchers and informants. This method was chosen because the analysis cannot be in the form of numbers, and researchers prefer to describe all phenomena that exist in society clearly. This research was carried out in stages according to a predetermined schedule, namely, to obtain complete data. The data that has been obtained from the interview process is then presented in the form of descriptions using words that are easy to understand and comprehend (Cohen et al., 2002). This research was conducted in RW 023 Teluk Pucung Village, North Bekasi District, Bekasi City, West Java. This research was carried out using descriptive qualitative methods. The data collection technique used was purposive sampling with a total of 10 people and consisted of elements of the community, RW, and local security forces. The data that has been obtained will be analyzed using nVivo and content analysis.

Results and Discussions

Crime is still rampant in the neighbourhoods where people live, one of which is in Bekasi City, the place where this research was conducted. Based on research conducted by interviewing 10 informants from the community of Teluk Pucung Village, North Bekasi District, Bekasi City in RW 023 has various crimes. Paul Moedikdo Moeliono (Muliadi, 2015), defines crime as an act of violating legal norms that justify or strengthen society as an act that is detrimental, disturbing and should not be tolerated. Based on interviews conducted some time ago, a common understanding was found between the community and the local government. On average, they understand a crime as a detrimental action that must be watched out for, one of which is theft.

Theft is an unlawful act of taking something belonging to another person that is intended to be owned. According to the Criminal Code, theft is the act of taking someone else's property against that person's existing rights. The crime of theft is regulated in Chapter XXIV Article 476 to Article 481 of Law no. 1 of 2023 concerning the Criminal Code. This is also stated in Article 476 of the Criminal Code (KUHP) which states "Any person who takes an item which partly or wholly belongs to another person, with the intention of possessing it unlawfully, shall be punished for theft, with a maximum prison sentence. 5 (five) years or a maximum fine of category V."

Theft that often disturbs residents and the local government is the theft of valuables, such as money and vehicles, which is carried out at night. Based on Article 477 of the Criminal Code (KUHP), perpetrators who are found to have committed criminal acts as above will be subject to sanctions in the form of imprisonment for a maximum of 7 years and a fine of up to category V. In addition, according to what residents said during interviews, the perpetrators also often break into people's houses using sharp weapons or chemical liquids to carry out their actions. So, based on Article 477 of the Criminal Code (KUHP), the perpetrator faces a maximum prison sentence of 9 years.

Apart from acts of theft, the local community and government often encounter incidents of brawls carried out by local students. This incident is juvenile delinquency, which can be caused by poor economic conditions, disharmonious families, and environmental influences. Adolescence is a time when children need their parents to be able to direct them in a positive direction because, during this period, teenagers have an unstable emotional level (fluctuating). So teenagers will easily get emotional. If this stage is not accompanied by proper control by parents, then incidents of juvenile delinquency, such as brawls, will continue to haunt people's lives. This is also mentioned by WHO (World Health Organization), namely that there is a role for family and parents in children's lives, such as being able to monitor children's activities,

control children's social environment, and the relationship between parents and children. Through these roles, children who are in the teenage phase will tend to feel safe and have positive mental health so they can avoid events related to juvenile delinquency.

Apart from the discovery of acts of theft and student brawls, the community also discovered drug abuse and alcohol consumption. Generally, perpetrators will carry out their actions at night while gambling or playing cards. The government regulates drug abuse as the use of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and addictive substances, which are not in accordance with their function and are regulated in the Latest Criminal Code in the fifth part of Chapter XXXV articles 609 - 611. Legal traps that threaten drug abusers based on the Criminal Code (KUHP) vary greatly, ranging from two years to 20 years, likewise, with the legal traps that threaten liquor consumers as described in Article 424 of the Criminal Code (KUHP).

Causes of Crime in the RW 023 Area

A number of factors certainly cause the occurrence of crime in an area. Among these factors are the economy, juvenile delinquency, and the environment. In the case of crimes that occurred in the RW 023 area, based on previous interviews, residents said that the factors that caused crimes to occur were economic level and environment/social relations.

Economic Factors

The interview agenda conducted some time ago revealed the fact that there was visible economic inequality between the residents of RW 023. Residential settlements in the RW 023 area were divided into two types, namely BTN housing and slums. This condition occurred as a result of the liberation carried out by the New Order government. At first, village residents relied on gardening on government-owned land for their subsistence needs. However, during the New Order era, the government acquired land which was used to build BTN housing for civil servants (PNS). As a result, village residents have to rack their brains to be able to meet their daily needs. Currently, they have professions whose income

is flexible, such as public transportation drivers, travelling salesmen, parking attendants, or opening stalls at their homes. The irregular income and the high demands of life make them inevitably commit acts of theft. The stolen goods will then be resold, and they will get wages.

Environmental/Social Factors

The low economic conditions of the residents then result in family relationships that are not close. This can be seen from the way the residents are raised, who tend to be indifferent to their children and only focus on "stomach matters." as a result, the children's education is neglected, and they grow up without any supervision and control from the family. So it will be very easy for them to fall into negative associations and make them become juvenile delinquents or perpetrators of other crimes. In this case, education plays an essential role in returning individuals to a positive direction. So, to reduce the number of crimes that occur, residents in residential areas form a foundation that helps residents in the field of education. Through this program, it is hoped that children and their parents will be able to form a positive environment.

Handling and Countermeasures by the Regional Government of RW 023

It was previously said that crimes across the RW 023 area varied greatly, from theft to sexual harassment. Based on what residents and the local government (RT and RW) said, if a crime is discovered, it will be handled in the RT area. If the RT area still needs to be finished, then the handling will continue to the RW area. In handling, people generally use family mediation techniques.

Mediation is an effort to resolve conflict that involves a third party as a mediator. Generally, mediation is used as an initial stage in resolving the conflict between the perpetrator of the crime and the victim before proceeding to court. If a mediated settlement does not produce good results for the victim, the perpetrator of the crime will be handled by the Babinsa/Babinkamtibnas at the police station. However, often, the perpetrator and his family

will try to ensure that their case does not end up in court so that, again, the victim will allow the perpetrator to go free with certain conditions. Settlement through mediation will involve the RT Head and several elders in the area. If the RT area has not been resolved, then mediation will be carried out by the RW Chair and his staff.

Regarding crime prevention, the community and local government usually appeal to people to protect themselves and their families. This appeal was also made by the sub-district government through the Head of Teluk Pucung Village or the sub-district secretary when visiting the RW 023 area. Apart from being addressed to residents at large, this appeal was also addressed to religious leaders or elders in the RW 023 area. As a preventive measure, not a few RTs have installed CCTV using residents' cash at a number of points and placed surveillance screens in the residents' halls so that many people can monitor them. The CCTV is placed in dark areas or corners around residential areas.

Conclusions

Indonesian society still comes into contact quite frequently with crime in the environment where they live, including the Teluk Pucung Village area, Bekasi, West Java. Crimes that often occur include theft, student brawls, and drug abuse. The community of RW 023, Teluk Pucung Village, Bekasi, West Java, understands the scope of crime and the handling of crimes that occur, so the role of government in this community is quite effective. The community and local government in the RW 023 area, Teluk Pucung Village, Bekasi, West Java, have understood the causes and countermeasures that must be taken to prevent crime from occurring in the area.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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